

Surface water quality assessment of Harmu and Subarnarekha River Basin, India using index mapping

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, an effort has been made to develop a methodology to integrate the Water quality index (WQI) with geographic information system (GIS) for an effective interpretation of the quality and health status of the Harmu River basin and Subarnarekha River basin. HRB and SRB has been taken as a case study. The physical, chemical and biological analysis has been interpreted using WQI. Based on the results of the analyses, spatial distribution maps of selected water quality parameters were prepared using GIS platform. A significant degradation in the WQ of the stations located in the lower reaches of the river basin is observed. Harmu mukti dham is the most polluted station followed by Hatia and Gatalsud station. The most inferior WQ with OIP value of 4.20 (polluted class) is observed in the pre-monsoon season of 2020 Gatalsud station. The OIP based on the individual index values was estimated giving the values in terms of pollution indices.

Index Terms—Water quality index (WQI), Geographic information system (GIS), Overall index of pollution (OIP), River Harmu and Subarnarekha basin (GRB) and Water quality (WQ).

1. INTRODUCTION

River Harmu and Subarnarekha has its extreme importance in Jharkhand, India. Almost 15% of the total population is directly or indirectly dependent on this river. Due to increased anthropogenic activities in the Subarnarekha River basin, the quantity and quality of river water are adversely affected. Water quality is a vital indicator of river basin health. For better river basin design and management, the information is necessary on the state of water quality and the variations occurring within it. Water is a very essential and precious natural resource for sustaining life on this planet. Owing to the increase in population and indiscriminate utilization, this vital resource is now under tremendous pressure. A complete understanding of water quality issues, it is important to translate it to a language understandable to policy makers [12]. The purpose of the OIP (overall index of pollution) is to integrate complex data and generate a score that defines water quality status and assesses water quality trends [4], [18]. Even though some facts are missing while integrating multiple water quality variables, this loss is outweighed by the gain in understanding of water quality issues by the public and policy makers [14], [15]. This study concentrates on determination and assessment of water quality of Harmu River basin and Subarnarekha River basin using OIP index and finally depicting it using geographical information system (GIS). The index method was firstly suggested by Horton [16]. Since then the use of indices is strongly suggested by agencies responsible for water supply. Water Quality Index (WQI) was introduced to generate a single value for the water quality of a source. Numerous water quality indices have been formulated all over the world like National sanitation foundation- WQI [17], Oregon WQI [7], British Columbia WQI [6], Canadian Council of Minister of the Environment -WQI [8] to assess the water quality. To resolve the problems related to data management and accessing the success and failures in managing strategies for improving water quality, the water quality index seems to be an effective and efficient index. In response to an effective way, so many indices were established in order to communicate the water quality data to the common public. The water quality indices integrate the multiple quality parameters and thus transforms to a mathematical expression that correlates the health of water quality and represents in a single number. The number obtained is placed to a scale of relative representation and divides the classes ranging from poor to outstanding. Thus the value is a clear representation of the quality of water which can be clearly understood by a layman and non-technical and decision makers can make the decision as this approach is subjective in nature. There are various water quality indices available to assess the water quality of different countries based on their own water quality standards.

2. BACKGROUND WORK AND OBJECTIVES

Rivers supply valuable drinking water to people, irrigation water to farmlands and provide habitat for many flora and fauna. Rapid industrialization and consequent urbanization have led to several problems

of water quality management of rivers. Water quality indices were presented with the purpose of decreasing the excessive amount of parameters into a simpler expression and allowing very easy analysis of observing datasets. In the groundwater, studies have been Carried out to assess irrigation water quality [10], [5] or spatial distribution of various chemical indices like pH, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids etc. using indices and GIS [13]. However, the literature available for surface water mainly deals with either the case study of the river using a WQI [3] or comparison of various WQI for a single source [1]. Surface water specific GIS tools like Index of Potential Non-point pollution (PNPI) do find a mention [9], [11], but an integrated approach of WQI with GIS has rarely been reported. This paper intends to fill this gap in surface water studies by uniting the two approaches. The main objective of this study is to assess the pollution status of river water quality through analysis of some selected water quality parameters and interpreting the water quality using index mapping. GIS are efficient aids for such study.

3. STUDY AREA

The Subarnarekha basin extends over States of Jharkhand, Odisha and comparatively smaller part in West Bengal having a total area of 29,196 Sq.km with a maximum length and width of about 297 km and 119 km. It lies between 85°8' to 87°32' east longitudes and 21°15' to 23°34' north latitudes. Situated in the north-east corner of the Peninsular India, the basin is bounded by the Chhotanagpur plateau on the north and the west, by the ridges separating it from Baitarani basin on the south, by the Bay of Bengal on the south-east and by the Kasai Valley of Kangsabati River on the east. The Subarnarekha and the Burhabalang forms the major river systems in the basin. The Subarnarekha River rises near Nagri village in the Ranchi District of Jharkhand at an elevation of 600 m. It flows for a length of 395 km before outfalling into the Bay of Bengal. Its principal tributaries joining from right are the Kanchi, the Karkari and the Kharkai. The Burhabalang rises from south of Similipal village in the Mayurbhanj district of Odisha at an elevation of about 800 m and flows for a length of 164 km and drains into the Bay of Bengal. The major part of basin is covered with agricultural land accounting to 53.76% of the total area and 2.39% of the basin is covered by water bodies.

Fig. 1: Location Map of Study Area

The study area is located between $85^{\circ} 07'$ to $85^{\circ} 34'$ E longitudes and $23^{\circ} 11'$ to $23^{\circ} 32'N$ at an average elevation 640 m above mean sea level. Study area witnessed rapid development during past decades in terms of urbanization, industrialization, and also population increase substantially. The river Harmu flows from west to north-east and it is the minor tributaries of Subarnarekha River. During the survey it was found that forest cover in the bank of Harmu River has almost non-existent. In addition to there was a large and small slum encroachments along the bank of the river. This encroachment of bank of the river has a resulted into a drastic situation where the Harmu river has slowly dried up. Summer temperatures range from $20^{\circ}C$ - $42^{\circ}C$ degrees whereas winter temperatures from $0^{\circ}C$ - $25^{\circ}C$ degrees.

4. DATA USED AND METHODOLOGY

In this study, two types of datasets are used: (i) Spatial datasets: (a) ASTER (Advanced Space borne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer) 1 arc-second global Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of 30 m spatial resolution derived from NASA, LP DAAC (National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Centre and (ii) Non-spatial datasets acquired from various departments of Government of India: (a) Monthly water quality datasets of the year 2010-2022 from Central Water Commission (CWC) were collected viz. Hardness $CaCO_3$, Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Fluoride (F), Dissolved Oxygen% (DO%), and pH. (b) Water quality reports from Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), Jharkhand Pollution Control Board (JPCB), Jharkhand Environment Protection and Pollution Control Board, National Institute of Hydrology (NIH) and CWC. The study is conducted in two phases: (i) In the first phase, remote sensing and GIS techniques are used. First ASTER DEM datasets are utilized to delineate the basin

boundary. For a better interpretation and understanding of the analyzed results, the concentrations of various parameters at various locations were integrated with GIS. (ii) In the second phase, Individual Parameter Indices (IPIs) were calculated for each parameter at a given time interval. Finally, OIP (Overall index of pollution) is estimated for each water quality monitoring station across the Harmu and Subarnarekha River basin over a period of 2010 to 2022. OIP is assessed as the average of all the pollution indices (P_i) for single water quality parameter considered in this research work. The mathematical expression [2] is used for calculation of OIP as expressed in equation 1:

$$\text{OIP} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n P_i}{n} \quad (1)$$

Where P_i = pollution index for the i^{th} parameter. $i = 1, 2 \dots n$ and n = a number of parameters. Further, water quality parameters viz. Hardness CaCO_3 , Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Fluoride (F), Dissolved Oxygen% (DO%) and pH were studied in basins for the pre, post and monsoontime periods.

5. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

From the results, it was observed that uncontrolled population increase in Harmu river basin has resulted in the colossal changes in water quality of the river basin. OIP estimates across the river basin demonstrate that the water quality of Harmu mukti dham and Hatia dam remain in acceptable class for all the three seasons except for July and November 2016. At Harmu mukti dham, the OIP is estimated to be 2.50 in monsoon month and 2.59 in the post-monsoon month. These observation stations are surrounded by hills and due to less population, they are not much influenced by human intervention. The river at these locations has high stream flow and the waste generated in these areas is treated well before discharging it to the river. Therefore, in the upper reach segment of the river basin, change in the water quality of Gatal sud dam and Hatia dam stations is mainly influenced by the generation of silts and climatic factor such as rainfall. A significant degradation in the water quality of the stations located in the lower reaches of the river basin is observed from the year 2010-2022 as shown in Table 1 (i) and (ii). This sharp deterioration in the water quality of the Harmu and Subarnarekha river is attributed to the increasing pollution from industrial and urban areas. Daily a huge amount of untreated municipal wastes and industrial effluents are discharged into the river. Muri road bridge is the most polluted station followed by Jamshedpur downstream and Gatal sud dam. But the values are much higher at Hatia and Muri road bridge. The most inferior water quality with OIP value of 4.20 (polluted class) is observed in the pre-monsoon season of 2015 at Varanasi station. Other than this most of the time the water quality at all the three stations remained in the acceptable to the slightly polluted range. From the temporal study of OIP across these stations, it is noticed that the water quality has deteriorated at all three stations from

2010 to 2022. The pre-monsoon season experienced the highest OIP values followed by post- monsoon season. River water quality is affected due to rainfall and increased stream flow during monsoon and post- monsoon season. During rainfall, different water quality parameters behave differently. This phenomenon is very sitespecific. Runoff generated from the rainfall discharges pollutants from the land surface to the nearby stream, but it also improves the river water quality by dissolving and transporting pollutants to other places through various natural processes. Geospatial technologies along with OIP are advantageous in studying water quality changes across a large river basin. The proposed OIP clubbed with GIS platform can be directly used to analyze and compare the situations across river basins and to identify trends over time. It is also suitable for representing deficiency of water quality and the health of water quality management practices. Therefore, water quality assessment using OIP could help to manage the available water resources sustainably. The future scope of this study comprises the understanding of hydrologic and ecological response of the water quality variations across the river basin.

Table 1 (i) and (ii) Individual parameter indices (IPIs) and overall indices of pollution (OIPs) computed at various water quality monitoring stations of Harmu and Subarnarekha river basin over periods of 2010-2022 for the pre-monsoon season.

PARAMETER	WATER QUALITY MONITORING STATIONS				
	HATIA DAM	GATALSUD DAM	MURI ROAD BRIDGE	CHANDIL DAM	JAMSHEDPUR DOWN STREAM
	JUNE	JUNE	JUNE	JUNE	JUNE
BOD	2.8	2.8	1.8	2.67	1.67
DO	1.2	1.2	1.38	1.27	1.20
F	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
HARDNESS(CACO ₃)	1.74	1.80	1.98	1.95	1.99
pH	2.8	2.8	2.52	3.4	3.4
TOTAL COLIFORM	-	-	-	3.42	4.12
TURBIDITY	-	-	1.00	1.00	1.00
OIP(2010)	2.11	2.12	1.78	2.24	2.19

PARAMETER	WATER QUALITY MONITORING STATIONS				
	HATIA DAM	GATALSUD DAM	MURI ROAD BRIDGE	CHANDIL DAM	JAMSHEDPUR DOWN STREAM
	JUNE	JUNE	JUNE	JUNE	JUNE
BOD	2.8	2.8	3.47	2.50	1.35
DO	2.35	1.32	1.45	1.45	1.00
F	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
HARDNESS(CACO3)	1.00	1.00	2.11	1.94	1.90
pH	2.09	2.09	3.52	3.30	4.45
TOTAL COLIFORM	-	-	-	4.05	4.15
TURBIDITY	-	-	1.00	1.00	1.00
OIP(2022)	2.04	1.84	2.25	2.17	2.26

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